

Innovative feeding strategies for high-yielding dairy animals: Advancing health, productivity and welfare

Anand Kumar Pathak^{1*}, Gaganjot Kour², Ashutosh Adalti², Abhay Singh², Pranav Kumar³ and Dhirendra Kumar⁴

¹Associate Professor, Division of Animal Nutrition, Faculty of Veterinary Sciences and AH, SKUAST-J, R S Pura-181102, Jammu

²MVSc Scholar, Division of Animal Nutrition, Faculty of Veterinary Sciences and AH, SKUAST-J, R S Pura-181102, Jammu

³Associate Professor, Division of VAHEE, Faculty of Veterinary Sciences and AH, SKUAST-J, R S Pura-181102, Jammu

⁴ Associate Professor, Department of AGB, COVSc & AH, Kishanganj, BASU, Patna, Bihar

*Corresponding author: dranandpathak1974@gmail.com

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Abstract

High milk-yielding dairy animals require innovative feeding strategies to meet their nutritional demands while ensuring health, production efficiency, and sustainability. Conventional feeding practices often fail to optimize nutrient utilization, leading to metabolic disorders and environmental concerns. The integration of innovative feeding strategies such as precision feeding and nutrition, condensed tannin (CT)-containing feed resources (LMMs, MNBs and DCFBs), chelated/ organic minerals, and nanotechnology-based feed supplements offers promising solutions to enhance nutritional efficiency, immune function, milk quality, and animal welfare. The mechanisms of action of these innovations are analyzed, along with their economic feasibility, highlighting their potential to reduce feed costs, enhance productivity, and support sustainable dairy farming.

Keywords: Dairy animals, Health, Innovative feeding strategies, Productivity, Welfare

Introduction

High yielding dairy animals (cows and buffaloes) require precise nutritional management including well-balanced nutrition, efficient feeding strategies and health-supportive interventions to maximize productivity, maintain well-being and enhance milk quality and quantity (Erickson and Kalscheur, 2020). Traditional feeding methods often fail to meet the evolving demands of high-producing dairy animals and often lead to metabolic disorders, nutrient wastage and environmental concerns (increased methane emissions), necessitating innovative approaches and novel dietary interventions in dairy animals' management. Recent innovations, including ration balancing, total mixed ration (TMR) (Zhang *et al.*, 2021), condensed tannin (CT)-containing feed resources (Pathak *et al.*, 2015, 2016, 2017a,b; Singh *et al.*, 2016; Khan *et al.*, 2019), chelated minerals, nutrigenomics (Kore *et al.*, 2008; Pathak, 2017a) and nanotechnology-based feed supplements (Singh, 2016), offer promising solutions to improve nutrient utilization, immune function, milk quality and quantity, and overall sustainability and welfare.

The recent advancements in feeding strategies include CT-containing feed resources, which enhance protein efficiency, gut health, and environmental sustainability (Pathak *et al.*, 2013, 2016, 2017a,b). Dietary supplementation of chelated minerals improves mineral absorption, immune function and reproductive performance (Gayathri and Panda, 2018). Nanotechnology-based feed supplements offer higher bioavailability, controlled nutrient release, and enhanced milk quality (Mukhtar *et al.*, 2015). These feeding innovations optimize nutrient utilization, reduce methane emissions, and improve animal welfare, making them integral to the future of sustainable and profitable dairy farming (Weiss *et al.*, 2006; Feng *et al.*, 2010; Wang *et al.*, 2013; Yattoo *et al.*, 2013; Singh, 2016; Pathak *et al.*, 2017b).

This article explores advanced feeding strategies including the role of CT-containing leaf meal mixtures (CT-LMM), multi-nutrient blocks (CT-MNB), densified complete feed blocks (CT-DCFB), chelated minerals, and nanotechnology that optimize dairy animal nutrition, production efficiency (milk yield), improve animal health, ensure sustainability in dairy farming and promote overall welfare.

Nutritional innovations for high milk yield

Precision nutrition and balanced rations

Formulating rations based on the specific requirements of high-yielding dairy cows ensures optimal milk production and overall health (Girard and Duplessis, 2022). Precision nutrition includes:

Energy optimization: Balancing carbohydrates, fats, and proteins to meet the energy demands of lactation and prevent metabolic disorders like ketosis and fatty liver.

Protein and amino acid supplementation: Using by-pass proteins (rumen undegradable protein) and essential amino acids such as lysine and methionine improves milk yield and composition.

Fat-soluble and water-soluble vitamin supplementation: When formulating diets for dairy animals, remember to include vitamin supplementation, particularly vitamins A, D, E and B12, whereas, ruminants produce enough vitamin K and other water-soluble vitamins in their rumen (Girard and Duplessis, 2022).

Fibre and rumen health: Maintaining an ideal fibre-to-concentrate ratio enhances rumen fermentation, preventing acidosis and ensuring efficient nutrient utilization.

Total mixed ration (TMR) and partial mixed ration (PMR)

TMR ensures a consistent and nutritionally balanced feed intake, preventing selective feeding and improving digestibility (Zhanget al., 2021; Panyawoot et al., 2022). PMR combines concentrates with roughage to allow for controlled nutrient intake.

Rumen-protected nutrients

Incorporating rumen-protected:

Fats: (Calcium salts of fatty acids) improve energy density without compromising fibre digestion (Soltan et al., 2018).

Proteins: Ensure higher post-rumen amino acid absorption, reducing nitrogen losses and environmental impact (Ali et al., 2009).

Vitamins and minerals: Enhance absorption and bioavailability, reducing deficiencies in high-yielding dairy animals.

Nutrigenomics and personalized nutrition

Using genetic insights to formulate individualized feeding programs enhances feed efficiency and milk production while minimizing metabolic stress and diseases (Kore et al., 2008; Pathak, 2017a).

Feed additives for enhanced performance

Probiotics and prebiotics

Probiotics (Lactobacillus, Saccharomyces cerevisiae): Improve gut microbiota balance, digestion, and immune response (Mohamed, 2013; Khan et al., 2016).

Prebiotics (Mannan-oligosaccharides, Fructo-oligosaccharides): Enhance beneficial microbial growth and gut health.

Enzymes and yeast culture

Fibre-degrading enzymes: Improve fibre digestibility, increase energy availability (Soltan *et al.*, 2013).

Yeast cultures: Enhance rumen microbial activity, stabilize pH and improve nutrient absorption.

Phytogetic feed additives (PFAs)

PFAs are plant-derived bioactive compounds (essential oils, flavonoids, condensed tannins; CTs, saponins, alkaloids) that improve digestion, immunity, and milk composition. Herbs, essential oils, and plant extracts (garlic, oregano, fenugreek, condensed tannins extract, etc.) improve digestion, immunity, and feed efficiency (Patra, 2011; Morsy *et al.*, 2021; Kour *et al.*, 2023; Kholif *et al.*, 2020).

Antimicrobial properties: Reduce pathogenic bacterial load, promote gut health.

Antioxidant activity: Reduces oxidative stress and improves milk shelf life.

Improved rumen fermentation: Enhances volatile fatty acid (VFA) production, optimizing energy utilization.

Milk quality enhancement: Increases fatty acid profile and antioxidant capacity of milk. Such as CTs from tree leaves (guava, jamun, and quebracho, etc.) modulate rumen microbiota and reduce methane emissions.

CTs and functional feed components in dairy nutrition

The CTs, plant secondary metabolites (PSMs), have protein-binding, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anthelmintic and methane-reducing properties that enhance nutrient utilization and animal health (Pathak, 2013, 2017b; Pathak *et al.*, 2015, 2016, 2017a,b). However, their inclusion in dairy diets requires careful formulation to avoid excessive intake, which may impair digestion. CTs bind dietary proteins in the rumen, preventing excessive degradation. The bound proteins bypass the rumen, undergoing enzymatic digestion in the small intestine, enhancing amino acid absorption and milk protein synthesis (Pathak *et al.*, 2015, 2016, 2017a,b). CTs modulate rumen fermentation and reduce methanogenic archaea populations, leading to lower methane emissions and improved feed energy utilization (Pathak *et al.*, 2017b). CTs exhibit antimicrobial properties, promoting beneficial gut microbiota while reducing pathogenic bacteria. Their antioxidant activity improves immune function (Pathak *et al.*, 2017a) and milk quality.

Benefits of CT in dairy feeding

Improved protein utilization: CT binds dietary proteins in the rumen, reducing its degradation and enhancing post-ruminal absorption, improving milk protein synthesis.

Enhanced gut health: Modulates rumen microbial populations, reducing pathogenic bacteria and improving fibre digestion.

Reduced methane emissions: Lowers enteric methane production, contributing to sustainable dairy farming.

Improved immunity: Enhances antioxidant capacity and immune responses, reducing disease susceptibility.

CT-containing leaf meal mixtures (LMM) in dairy diets

The LMM from CT-containing trees (e.g., Guava, Jamun, Leucaena, Acacia, Sesbania, Albizia, and Ficus, etc.) offer a sustainable protein source while delivering functional bioactive compounds (Pathak *et al.*, 2015; 2016, 2017a,b; 2019; Ganai *et al.*, 2023).

Nutritional and production benefits

High crude protein and fibre content: Supports rumen health and milk yield.

Bypass protein supply: Reduces nitrogen losses, increasing protein bioavailability.

Methane reduction: Improves energy efficiency by reducing rumen methanogenesis.

Anthelmintic effects: Reduces parasite burdens, improving digestion and feed conversion.

Impact on milk yield and composition

Higher milk protein and fat: Due to better amino acid absorption.

Improved milk antioxidant capacity: Leads to better shelf-life and quality.

Lower somatic cell count (SCC): Enhances udder health and milk hygiene.

Feeding strategies

Incorporation in TMR: Up to 15% LMM can improve milk yield without adverse effects.

Fermented leaf meal inclusion: Enhances nutrients bioavailability and feed palatability.

CT-containing multi-nutrient blocks (MNBs)

MNBs are solidified feed supplements containing CTs, minerals, energy sources, and vitamins, formulated to enhance nutrient intake and rumen function in high-producing animals (Singh *et al.*, 2015a,b, 2016; Singh *et al.*, 2019; Kour *et al.*, 2022; Ganai *et al.*, 2025).

Advantages of CT-based MNBs

Sustained nutrient release: Reduces digestive fluctuations and stabilizes rumen fermentation.

Reduced urea excretion: Improves nitrogen retention and utilization.

Boosted immunity: Supports overall health and reproductive efficiency.

Enhanced feed efficiency: Stimulates microbial protein synthesis and fibre digestion.

Milk yield and composition improvement

Higher casein content: Enhances milk processing qualities.

Lower SCC and mastitis risk: Due to better immune function, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties.

Increased omega-3 fatty acids: From improved rumen bio-hydrogenation.

Recommended feeding approach

Daily MNB intake: 300–500 g per cow/ buffalo per day to optimize microbial balance.

CT-containing densified complete feed blocks (DCFBs)

DCFBs combine roughages, concentrates, minerals, and functional additives into balanced complete feed, ensuring balanced nutrition and reduced feed sorting (Khan *et al.*, 2017, 2019). These MNBs (Singh *et al.*, 2015a,b, 2016) and DCFBs incorporate CTs, minerals, protein, and energy sources, ensuring sustained nutrient availability and improved rumen function. These blocks provide a gradual supply of nutrients, improving digestibility and rumen stability (Khan *et al.*, 2017, 2019; Singh *et al.*, 2015a,b, 2016). Enhanced microbial protein synthesis results in higher milk yield and better feed conversion efficiency. Stabilized rumen fermentation reduces the risk of acidosis, ketosis, and milk fever (Pathak, 2025).

Nutritional and production benefits

Improved nutrient digestibility: Reduces wastage and selective feeding.

Optimized rumen fermentation: Stabilizes pH and microbial activity.

Consistent nutrient supply: Prevents metabolic disorders like acidosis and ketosis.

Improved lactation performance: Due to enhanced fibre digestion and energy utilization.

Effects on milk quality

Higher butterfat content: From better for digestion.

Improved lactose content: Due to enhanced energy metabolism.

Lower milk urea nitrogen (MUN): Reflecting better protein utilization.

Feeding strategies

DCFB intake: 4-6 kg and/or 8–10 kg per cow per day according to body weight and physiological condition of the animal, replacing conventional concentrate and roughages.

Chelated/Organic trace minerals for enhanced bioavailability

Replacing inorganic minerals with chelated or organic forms (zinc, selenium, copper manganese, etc.) improves bioavailability, immune function, and reproductive performance. Chelated minerals (zinc, copper, selenium, manganese) are bound to organic molecules (amino acids, peptides), and improve their absorption, bioavailability and retention. Chelated minerals bypass interactions with anti-nutritional factors, leading to superior absorption and retention

(Gayathri and Panda, 2018). They support enzyme activation, reproductive health, and immune function, reducing the incidence of mastitis, lameness, and reproductive disorders.

Benefits for dairy animals

Better reproductive efficiency: Reduces retained placenta and metritis.

Improved hoof health: Prevents lameness and mobility issues.

Stronger immune function: Lowers incidence of mastitis and metabolic disorders.

Impact on milk quality

Higher antioxidant levels: Reduces oxidative spoilage.

Lower heavy metal contamination: Due to controlled mineral intake.

Improved milk fat and protein ratio: Due to better metabolic balance.

Recommended inclusion rates

Zinc (Zn-methionine): 40–50 mg/kg DM for immune and hoof health (NRC, 2001).

Selenium (Se-yeast): 0.3–0.5 mg/kg DM for antioxidant defence (NRC, 2001).

Nanotechnology in dairy nutrition

Nanotechnology improves nutrient absorption, bioavailability, and metabolic efficiency through nano-encapsulated supplements and nano-particle-based feed additives. Nanotechnology enables the encapsulation of nutrients, leading to controlled release, improved solubility, and enhanced absorption. Nano-minerals (Zn, Se, and Fe) showed higher bioavailability leading to better metabolic efficiency and immune resilience. Nano-encapsulated vitamins and probiotics improved gut health, milk quality, and stress tolerance. Nano-fatty acid supplements enhance energy utilization, milk fat composition, and oxidative stability (Shi *et al.*, 2011; Sabry, *et al.*, 2018).

Benefits of nano-based feeding innovations

Higher absorption efficiency: Nano-minerals and vitamins exhibit superior bioavailability.

Enhanced gut health: Protects against pathogenic bacteria.

Controlled nutrient release: Reduces feed wastage and improves metabolic efficiency.

Nano-minerals for dairy performance

Nano-zinc: Enhances immunity, and reduces mastitis risk.

Nano-selenium: Improves antioxidant capacity and milk stability.

Nano-iron: Prevents anaemia and enhances oxygen transport.

Impact on milk quality

Increased shelf life: Due to higher antioxidant activity.

Enhanced nutrient composition: Better mineral and vitamin profiles.

Recommended dosage

Nano-zinc: 20–40 ppm in diet for optimal immune function.

Nano-selenium: 0.1–0.3 ppm for antioxidant benefits.

Feeding strategies to improve milk quality

Improving fat and protein content

Omega-3 fatty acids (flaxseed, fish oil): Improve milk fat composition and reduce inflammatory responses.

By-pass protein sources (soybean meal, canola meal): Increase casein content, improving milk processing quality.

Reducing somatic cell count (SCC) and enhancing udder health

Vitamin E and selenium: Strengthen immune responses, reducing mastitis incidence.

Aloe vera and herbal feed supplements: Provide anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects.

Reducing antibiotic residues through natural alternatives

Phytogenic additives and probiotics reduce the reliance on antibiotics while maintaining milk quality.

Welfare-centric feeding innovations

Heat stress mitigation through nutrition

Electrolyte supplementation (Sodium, Potassium and Bicarbonates): Prevents dehydration and heat stress.

Betaine and antioxidants: Improve thermoregulation and milk yield during heat stress periods.

Precision feeding for transition cows and buffaloes

Close-up diets: Focus on high-energy, low-calcium diets to prevent milk fever.

Fresh cow diets: Include high-quality forages and controlled starch levels to minimize metabolic disorders.

Pasture-based and grazing innovations

Rotational grazing: Improves nutrient intake, reduces feed costs, and enhances cow welfare.

Silvo-pastoral system: Integrate trees and shrubs for improved nutrient diversity and shade.

Sustainability and economic viability

Reducing feed wastage and improving digestibility

Precision feeding technologies: Automated feeders and real-time nutrient tracking minimize wastage.

Feed processing (Pelleting and extrusion, etc.): Enhances digestibility and reduces sorting behaviour.

Although initial costs increase in adopting innovative feeding strategies (Wang *et al.*, 2018), however, the improved feed efficiency, higher milk yield, and reduced health expenses justify profitable and sustainable CT-based feeding strategies (Singh *et al.*, 2015a, b, 2016; Khan *et al.*, 2017, 2019). Despite higher costs, improved absorption and reduced wastage make chelated minerals economically viable. While nanotechnology is expensive, the enhanced bioavailability and long-term productivity benefits make it a cost-effective investment for high-yielding cows.

Environmental benefits

Lower nitrogen and methane emissions: Sustainable CT-based (LMMs, MNBs and DCFBs) feeding significantly reduced urinary nitrogen excretion and enteric methane emission in ruminants which ultimately decreased environmental pollution (Pathak, 2013; Pathak *et al.*, 2017b). Efficient nutrient utilization minimizes nutrient losses; reduces enteric methane emissions and environmental pollution.

Conclusion

Innovative feeding strategies are essential for sustaining high milk production while ensuring animal health, welfare, and economic efficiency. Precision nutrition, advanced feed additives, and sustainable practices enhance dairy performance and milk quality. Integrating CT-containing feed resources (CT-containing LMMs, MNBs, DCFBs), chelated minerals, and nanotechnology-based supplements significantly improve nutrient utilization and nutritional efficiency, health, milk yield and quality, and welfare in high-yielding dairy cows.

The mechanisms of action highlight their role in optimizing digestion, immunity, and metabolic efficiency, while economic feasibility assessments demonstrate their cost-effectiveness in long-term dairy productivity. These innovations optimize rumen fermentation, immune function, and nutrient bioavailability, leading to sustainable dairy production with improved profitability. By integrating science-driven nutritional approaches, dairy farmers can achieve optimal productivity while maintaining ethical and sustainable dairy farming practices. Future research should focus on optimizing CT inclusion rates, developing advanced nano-feed supplements, and assessing long-term impacts on dairy productivity and environmental sustainability.

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